

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The proverb is an important part of the folklore and they are consecrated fortunes of individuals' way of life and language. This article provides a comparative description of English and Karakalpak proverbs. In addition, this research discusses the classification of English proverbs in relation to Karakalpak equivalents and the difficulties in translating from English proverbs.*

Keywords: *proverb, wisdom, linguistics, cultural, full equivalents, partial equivalents.*

РАЗЛИЧИЯ И СХОДСТВО ПОСЛОВИЦ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *Пословицы составляют важную часть фольклора и являются освященными судьбами образа жизни и языка отдельных людей. В данной статье дается сравнительная характеристика английских и каракалпакских пословиц. Кроме того, в данном исследовании рассматривается классификация английских пословиц по отношению к каракалпакским эквивалентам и трудности перевода с английских пословиц.*

Ключевые слова: *пословица, мудрость, языкознание, культурология, полные эквиваленты, частичные эквиваленты.*

INTRODUCTION

The values, traditions, characteristics and mentality of each nation are clearly reflected in their native language. That is why language is the treasure of the nation. We can see the specific features of national mentality, traditions, history and culture, especially in phraseological units. Analysis of phraseological units is related to external factors, for example: country's history, culture, lifestyle. In phraseological units, proverbs are related to events and include people's way of life, worldviews, political, religious, aesthetic views. Proverbs are a sharp tool of beautiful words that convey a lot of essence with few words and quickly affect the feeling. For this reason, proverbs have a portable meaning without excessive words that do not fit the thought [2:19]. The proverbs of all peoples have a common meaning, and at the same time, they reflect their own national culture based on the long history of each nation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Proverbs have a deep meaning of wisdom. Proverbs are passed down to future generations based on the way of life and life experiences of the people. That is why there are many proverbs that are close to each other in terms of content. If we compare proverbs in Karakalpak and English, proverbs are one of the most common genres of English folklore in English as well as in Karakalpak.

RESULTS

When translating proverbs from one language to another, rather than finding the direct translation of the proverb in the second language, it is more important to convey their main meaning through equivalents, because proverbs are folk-oral creations of each nation. In English and Karakalpak proverbs, we can see that some proverbs in these two languages correspond to each other in terms of lexical semantic, structural and linguistic features, so we analyzed the English and Karakalpak proverbs into several groups.

DISCUSSION

In the first group, we can include proverbs with full equivalents, because when we translate proverbs in this group, we can see that the words in both languages correspond to the full, including that they have common meanings. For instance:

- The apple doesn't fall from the tree - Alma tereginnen alisqa tu'speydi.
- Never put off till tomorrow what you can do today - Bu'gingi isti erenge qaldirma.
- Better late than never - Heshten ko're kesh jaqsi.
- Strike while the iron is hot - Temirdi qizg'anda bas.

The second group of proverbs consists of partial or similar equivalents: that is, when translating proverbs in English and Karakalpak languages, we witness the small number of words in their composition, but we can see variants with close meanings. For example:

- Much effort, much prosperity – Miynet - tu'bi ra'ha't.
- There is no place like home - O'z uyin' - o'len' to'segin'.
- Bad children guilty parents - Jaqsi perzent su'yinish, jaman perzent ku'yinish.
- He who is afraid of asking is ashamed of learning - Sorap u'yrengen alim, arlanip soramag'an o'zine zalim.

The third group includes proverbs that cannot be completely translated from English or Karakalpak, because the two languages use different lexicons. Therefore, in addition to the proverbs of the English language. There may not be a full or similar equivalent in the Karakalpak language, but in some cases the word and its meaning are close to each other. For example:

- When hens have teeth - Tas gu'llegende.
- Like father like son - A'kege qaray ul o'ser.
- When pigs fly - Tu'yenin' quyrig'i jerge tiygende.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, as a result of comparing the proverbs in the Karakalpak and English languages, we can be sure that we will see the national heritage of these two peoples in folk proverbs, because proverbs reflect all the thoughts, worldviews, ways of living, and behavior of the people. Although proverbs in English and Karakalpak languages are similar to each other, they are distinguished by the fact that the images in them are not repeated. For this reason, in order to understand proverbs in English, it is important to learn their meaning with the help of examples.

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